

THE IMPORTANCE OF GOVERNMENT SOVEREIGN BONDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

Akhmedova Shokhistakhon Asliddin kizi

Bachelor's degree student, Tashkent Institute of Finance

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7439663>

Annotation: This article analyzes the role of Eurobonds in the international capital market, the purpose of their issuance and their advantages for national economies. Moreover, statistical analysis of sovereign Eurobonds issued by the Government of Uzbekistan on the international stock market is analyzed.

Key words: bond, Eurobond, coupon rate, maturity, government sovereign Eurobonds, international capital market.

Introduction

The international capital market is both the result of the development of the world economy and the accelerator of this development. It contributes to the internationalization of production and the exchange of capital by creating favorable conditions for the movement of securities between countries. At the same time, it is also an additional source of net income, both in various forms of dividends and interest payments, and in the form of net speculative income, based on the difference in the prices of securities in different countries. The international capital market is necessary for the participants of capital markets in order to protect their investments from various kinds of market, currency and credit risks, as it creates additional opportunities for hedging and diversification of capital. The market of sovereign and corporate Eurobonds will attract capital and, most importantly, the attention of foreign investors to the stock market and the economy of Uzbekistan as a whole, which will provide an incentive in their development. Foreign investors will bring additional liquidity to the stock and bond market in Uzbekistan, which is so necessary for us, will allow local companies to efficiently place bond loans in the local market, increase the cost of shares, which will allow the population and business to receive an additional source of income from the resale of their blocks of shares.

Literature review

Capital markets are for securities with an original maturity that is greater than one year. These securities include bonds, stocks, and mortgages. Among the given types of securities bonds represent one of the most popular long-term alternatives to investing in stocks. **Bonds** are securities that represent a debt owed by the issuer to the investor. Bonds obligate the issuer to pay a specified amount at a given date, generally with periodic interest payments. The par, face, or maturity value of the bond is the amount that the issuer must pay at maturity.

The **coupon rate** is the rate of interest that the issuer must pay, and this periodic interest payment is often called the coupon payment. This rate is usually fixed for the duration of the bond and does not fluctuate with market interest rates. If the repayment terms of a bond are not met, the holder of a bond has a claim on the assets of the issuer. Bonds are lower risk than stocks because they have a higher priority of payment. This means that when the firm is having difficulty meeting its obligations, bondholders get paid before stockholders. Additionally, should the firm have to liquidate, bondholders must be paid before stockholders. [1]

Even healthy firms with sufficient cash flow to pay both bondholders and stockholders frequently have very volatile stock prices. This volatility scares many investors out of the stock market. Bonds are the most popular alternative. They offer relative security and dependable cash payments, making them ideal for retired investors and those who want to live off their investments. Many investors think that bonds represent a very low risk investment since the cash flows are relatively certain. It is true that high-grade bonds seldom default; however, bond investors face fluctuations in price due to market interest-rate movements in the economy.

As interest rates rise and fall, the value of bonds changes in the opposite direction. The possibility of suffering a loss because of interest-rate changes is called **interest rate risk**. The longer the time until the bond matures, the greater will be the change in price. This does not cause a loss to those investors who do not sell their bonds; however, many investors do not hold their bonds until maturity. If they attempt to sell their bonds after interest rates have risen, they will receive less than they paid. Interest-rate risk is an important consideration when deciding whether to invest in bonds.

International bonds are bonds issued by a country or company that is not domestic for the investor. The international bond market is quickly expanding as countries and companies continue to look for the cheapest way to borrow money in order to implement new or ongoing projects. By issuing debt on an international scale, a company can reach more investors. It also potentially helps decrease regulatory constraints. There are three general categories for international bonds: domestic, euro, and foreign. The categories are based on the country of the issuer, the country of investor, and the currencies used.

Domestic bonds are issued, underwritten and then traded with the currency and regulations of the borrower's country. For example, an Uzbek company

issues debt in Uzbekistan with the principal and interest payments based or denominated in Uzbek soums.

Eurobonds are underwritten by an international company and denominated in a currency other than the home currency and then traded outside of the country's domestic market. For example, an Uzbek company issues debt in the United Kingdom with the principal and interest payments in denominated in US dollars.

Foreign bonds are issued in a domestic country by a foreign company, using the regulations and currency of the domestic country. For example, an Italian company issues debt in Uzbekistan with the principal and interest payments denominated in soums.

A Eurobond is a debt capital market instrument issued in a 'Eurocurrency' through a syndicate of issuing banks and securities houses, and distributed internationally when issued – that is, sold in more than one country of issue and subsequently traded by market participants in several international financial centres. [2]

Eurobonds are frequently grouped together by the currency in which they are denominated, such as eurodollar or euro-yen bonds. The Eurobond is a type of bond that is issued in a currency that is different from that of the country or market in which it is issued. Despite its name, it has no particular connection to Europe or the euro currency. Due to this external currency characteristic, these types of bonds are also known as external bonds. Eurobonds are important because they help organizations raise capital while having the flexibility to issue them in another currency. Issuance of Eurobonds is usually handled by an international syndicate of financial institutions on behalf of the borrower, one of which may underwrite the bond, thus guaranteeing the purchase of the entire issue. In history the first Eurobond was issued in 1963 by Autostrade, the company that ran Italy's national railroads. It was a \$15 million eurodollar bond designed by bankers in London, issued at Amsterdam Airport Schiphol and paid in Luxembourg to reduce taxes. It provided European investors with a safe, dollar-denominated investment.

Issuers run the gamut from multinational corporations to sovereign governments and supranational organizations. The size of a single bond issuance can be well over a billion dollars, and maturities are between five and 30 years, although the largest portion has a maturity of fewer than 10 years. Eurobonds are especially attractive to issuers based in countries that do not have a large capital market while offering diversification to investors.

Analysis and results

The global bond market totals over \$100 trillion in outstanding debt. The fact many Eurobonds are unregistered, and trade-in bearer form makes definitive numbers for the sector impossible to obtain, but it is likely they account for about 30% of the total. A growing portion of Eurobond issuance is from emerging market nations, with both governments and companies seeking deeper and more developed markets in which to borrow. There are lots of benefits of Eurobonds for issuers and investors.

There are a number of benefits to issuing Eurobonds rather than domestic bonds for a project of this type for the issuer:

- ✓ Companies can issue bonds in the country of their choice and the currency of their choice, depending on what is most beneficial for the planned use;
- ✓ The issuer can choose a country with an interest rate that is favorable to its own at the time of the issue, thus reducing the costs of borrowing;
- ✓ Eurobonds have particular appeal to certain investor populations. For example, many U.K. residents with roots in India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh view investments in their homelands favorably;
- ✓ The company reduces forex risk. For example, the company could have issued the domestic bonds in the US in US dollars, converted the amount to the domestic currency of the issuer's country at the prevailing rates in order to move it to the home country, then exchanged the domestic currency for US dollars in order to pay interest to bondholders. This process adds transactional costs and forex rate risk;
- ✓ Although Eurobonds are issued in a particular country, they are traded globally, which helps in attracting a large investor base.

The benefits of Eurobonds for the investor are these:

- ✓ Eurobonds can offer diversification with a smaller degree of risk. They are investing in a solid and familiar local company that is expanding its business into an emerging market;
- ✓ Eurobonds are denominated in foreign currencies but launched in nations with strong currencies. That keeps them highly liquid for their local investors.

Nowadays nearly all developing countries issued their sovereign Eurobonds to finance important projects. Like other developing countries, for the first time in its history, Uzbekistan placed \$ 1 billion Eurobonds on February 14, 2019. The bonds were placed in a double tranche of \$ 500 million maturing in February 2024 and 2029, the press service of the Ministry of Finance said. Typically,

Eurobonds are issued to attract borrowed capital in the interests of the country, for example, to develop large projects, finance the activities of current sectors of the economy, etc. But Uzbekistan had completely different goals. First of all, as representatives of the government note, the issuance and successful placement of sovereign bonds on European platforms should become a benchmark for subsequent issues of corporate Eurobonds by leading enterprises of the country, because the demand for financing in the country is very high: the revitalization of the business has led to the emergence of new projects, requiring large capital investments in construction, the purchase of advanced equipment, technologies, attracting qualified personnel. The better the placement of sovereign Eurobonds will take place; the cheaper public and private companies will be able to raise funds within corporate placements. In addition, access to international capital markets will significantly increase competition in the domestic market, which will reduce the cost of attracting debt, as at the moment there is only the possibility of attracting bank loans and capital from founders on the market, which is often quite expensive types of financing investment projects and often does not allow companies to implement expensive low-margin projects of an infrastructural nature or having a long implementation period. In July 2018, the government of Uzbekistan engaged a consortium of banks led by JP Morgan Chase to obtain a sovereign credit rating and issue sovereign bonds. In accordance with the decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the funds received from the placement of bonds will be directed to the implementation of work under social programs and the construction of infrastructure facilities. According to experts, a sovereign rating acts as a way to diversify sources of attracting foreign funds. Obtaining a credit rating of the country will contribute to the growth of foreign direct investment, expand cooperation with foreign partners, as well as create favorable conditions for banks and enterprises to attract credit in the global financial markets at lower interest rates. Initially, the coupon rate range was set at 5,625 to 5.75 percent and 6 percent, but due to high demand, Uzbekistan reconsidered interest rates and reduced them to 4.75 percent and 5.375 percent. About \$ 3.8 billion in bids were received from about 150 institutional investors. From a state perspective, the majority of 5-year and 10-year bonds purchased were purchased by British investors (39% and 32%, respectively), while American investors purchased 23% and 31% of the bonds. European investors accounted for 32% and 27%, while investors from Asia, the Middle East and North Africa accounted for 6 and 10%. The majority of

Eurobonds - 75% and 78% - were bought by management funds, 20% and 16% by insurance companies and pension funds, 5% and 6% by banks.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4258 "On the effective use of funds from the placement of the first sovereign international bonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan", funds from Eurobonds were placed as shown in the table below. [3]

Table 1

**Placement of Eurobond loans as deposits between local organizations.[3]
(In thousand US dollars)**

	The amount of money received as a result of the issuance of Euro bonds	The amount of deposits in banks through the auction	Subordinated debt allocated for Agrobank	Loan from the budget allocated for Navoi Mining and Metallurgy Combine	The amount of interest accrued on the amount of money in banks as a deposit	The amount of interest accrued on subordinated debt allocated for Agrobank	The amount of interest accrued on the loan allocated for Navoi Mining and Metallurgy Combine	Annual interest income from the amount of money placed in banks as a deposit	Annual interest income from the subordinated debt allocated for Agrobank	Annual interest income from the loan allocated for Navoi Mining and Metallurgy Combine	Total annual interest income
5-year international	\$500,000	\$459,600	\$0	\$39,950	5.250%	0.000%	5.750%	\$24,129	\$0.00	\$2,297	\$26,426

nal bon ds											
10- yea r int ern atio nal bon ds	\$500, 000	\$429, 600	\$20, 000	\$49, 950	5.875 %	5.875 %	6.375 %	\$25, 239	\$1,17 5	\$3,18 4	\$29, 598
Tot al	\$1,00 0,000	\$889 ,200	\$20, 000	\$89, 900				\$49, 368	\$1,17 5	\$5,48 1	\$56, 024

According to Table 1, a total of \$ 889,200,000 was deposited in commercial banks through auctions at 5.25% and 5.875% over 5 and 10 years, respectively. In addition, a credit line of \$ 20 million was opened for Agrobank as a subordinate loan at 5.875% over 10 years. In addition, \$ 89.9 million was allocated as a budget loan to finance strategic projects for the Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine in two different terms. That's \$ 39.95 million at 5.75% over 5 years and \$ 49.95 million at 6.375% over 10 years.

Table 2

Coupon payments on 5-year and 10-year Eurobonds. (In Thousand US dollars)

	2020 year	2021 year	2022 year	2023 year	2024 year	2025 year	2026 year	2027 year	2028 year	2029 year	Total coup on paym ents of Euro bond s
Coupo n paym ents	\$23, 750	\$23,7 50	\$23,7 50	\$23,7 50	\$23,7 50						\$118, 750

of 5-year Eurobonds											
Coupon payments of 10-year Eurobonds	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$268,750
Total coupon payments of two types of Eurobonds	\$50,625	\$50,625	\$50,625	\$50,625	\$50,625	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$26,875	\$387,500
Accumulated expenses for total coupon payments	\$50,625	\$101,250	\$151,875	\$202,500	\$253,125	\$280,000	\$306,875	\$333,750	\$360,625	\$387,500	

As you can see from the data in this Table 2, the one-year coupon payment on 5-year Eurobonds is \$ 23,750,000, making the total five-year coupon payment on this type of Eurobonds \$ 118,750,000. For 10-year Eurobonds, the annual coupon payment is \$ 26,875,000 and the total ten-year coupon payment is \$ 268,750,000. The above two different-term Eurobonds are subject to coupon

payments totaling \$ 50,625,000 per year and a total of \$ 387,500,000 over ten years.

Table 3

Interest income on 5-year and 10-year Eurobonds. (In thousand US dollars)

	2020 year	2021 year	2022 year	2023 year	2024 year	2025 year	2026 year	2027 year	2028 year	2029 year	Total interest income
Interest income on 5-year Eurobonds	\$26,426	\$26,426	\$26,426	\$26,426	\$26,426						\$132,130
Interest income on 10-year Eurobonds	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$295,983
Total interest income on two types of Eurobonds	\$56,024	\$56,024	\$56,024	\$56,024	\$56,024	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$29,598	\$428,113
Accumulated	\$56,024	\$112,048	\$168,073	\$224,097	\$280,122	\$309,720	\$339,318	\$368,917	\$398,515	\$428,113	

total interest income on two types of Eurobonds											
---	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

According to Table 3 above, interest income from 5-year Eurobonds is \$ 26,426,000 per annum, while total five-year interest income is \$ 132,130,000. Annual interest income from 10-year Eurobonds is \$ 29,598,000, up from a total of \$ 295,983,000 over ten years. Summarizing the above data, the total interest income in one year will be \$ 56,024,000 and in ten years this figure will be \$ 428,113,000. Now, if we compare the data in tables 1 and 2 above, the total annual coupon payments are \$ 50,625,000, the total annual interest income is \$ 56,024,000, and the difference between them is \$ 5,399,000. This means that the net profit on Eurobonds in the first five years will be about \$ 27 million. The annual net profit for the next five years is \$ 2.72 million, for a total of \$ 13.6 million over the next five years. The net interest income for the decade will be \$ 40.6 million. It should be noted that the placement of the bulk of proceeds from the placement of international sovereign bonds as deposits in commercial banks does not increase state budget expenditures and does not incur additional costs from the budget.

Conclusions and proposals

Companies that have received financing through the issuance of Eurobonds are implementing projects that they would not have done without it or would have done less efficiently. Banks that attracted financing in international markets, redistribute them to small and medium-sized enterprises, which so far cannot use this tool because of the size of the business or its specifics. Another important positive change will be the increase in the qualifications of all organizations that have decided to enter international markets - the issuance of bonds imposes obligations on information disclosure, regular reporting, which should improve the quality of corporate governance, planning and budgeting. Local businessmen and the population interested in earning additional income in the stock market will significantly increase their knowledge of both the basic

tools and principles of its work, as well as best practices, which, of course, should be transferred to our market. Government Eurobonds, domestic loan bonds, corporate debt securities and capital development will later lead to the emergence of various types of derivatives and swaps. If at the initial stage a significant part of the market can be accounted for by foreign investors and trade on foreign markets, then with the expansion of the number of issuing companies, the number and types of investors, the local market should also increase its volume and take its place in a number of developed markets.

References:

1. Frederic S. Mishkin and Stanley G. Eakins (2015). Financial Markets and Institutions (Eight Edition) 704.
2. Moorad Choudhry (2006). An Introduction to Bond Markets (Third Edition) 152 p.
3. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: № PD-4258 dated April 2, 2019 "On the effective use of funds from the placement of the first sovereign international bonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan"

